

RESPONSE PAPER

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PROGRAM CODE: DSDD

COURSE CODE : ACA – 401D

PERIOD NUMBER: RP 6

INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author used the following software: (MSWord on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. In writing dissertation, how do you do in-text citation, using the Turabian style of writing? Tick the correct answer.**
 - By writing the date of publication only.
 - By writing inside a bracket, the surname of the author, year of publication and page that contains the text being cited.¹**
 - By writing the name of the author only.
 - By not writing anything.

- 2. When do you consider using comma, as a style for writing an essay or dissertation? Tick the correct answer.**
 - It is used for describing a sentence.
 - It is used for ending a sentence.
 - It is used interchangeably with full stop.

¹ Euclid University. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Located at: <http://www.eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>, 16.

- It is used for separating a sentence for better meaning, or for in-text citation of author, date and page being cited.²**
3. **Why do you need to cite your sources of information in dissertation writing? Tick the correct answer.**
- It is used to beautify the essay.
- It is to fulfill the requirement of the supervisor.
- It is to avoid plagiarism.³**
- No specific reason.
4. **When do you use “Ibid” in your dissertation writing? Tick the correct answer.**
- When citing a source.
- When citing multiple texts from the same page of a book being used for citation.⁴**
- When using multiple sources.
- When writing bibliography.
5. **When do you use footnotes in dissertation writing? Tick the correct answer.**
- When you want to make substantive comments on text.⁵**

² Kate L. Turabian. 2013. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. 8th edition. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing.* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press), 128.

³ Euclid University, 12.

⁴ Turabian, 99.

⁵ Turabian, 134.

- When you want to write a paragraph.
 - When you want to use comma.
 - When you want to write Latin.
6. **When do you use colon in dissertation writing? Tick the correct answer.**
- It is used to indicate that an expansion, qualification or explanation is about to follow.⁶**
 - It is used to analyse dissertation.
 - It is used to supplement parenthesis.
 - It is used in place of hyphen.
7. **What does the methodology section show, when writing the proposal for your dissertation? Tick the correct answer.**
- It shows the art of writing.
 - It shows how to go about, conducting the study.⁷**
 - It shows the reference and citation.
 - It depicts the volume and table of contents.
8. **What is the meaning of plagiarism in dissertation writing? Tick the correct answer.**

⁶ European Commission Directorate-General for Translation. 2011. *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission. 11th edition.*, 21.

⁷ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie Volpe. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End.* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc.), 19.

- It means writing texts in a dissertation, without acknowledging the sources where the information were received.⁸**
- It means writing dissertation without style.
- It means writing dissertation without bibliography.
- It means writing very well.
9. **What is the applicable citation management software used by EUCLID? Tick the correct answer.**
- It is called Navision.
- It is called Zotero.⁹**
- It is called Microsoft office.
- It is called Sage.
10. **What should the typical structure of an essay be? Tick the correct answer.**
- It should be writing without style.
- It should be paraphrasing.
- It should follow the sequence of; introduction, body and conclusion.¹⁰**

⁸ Euclid University, 9.

⁹ Turabian, 89.

¹⁰ Euclid University, 4.

- It should be twenty-page writing.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D. and Volpe Marie. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2008.

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